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**An Evaluation of Framework and implementation tool
for HEIs in Uganda****Gastervas Geoffrey Rutwara, Johnnie W. F. Muwanga-Zake, J.M.O. Tukei**
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University College Dublin**Abstract**

With fast-evolving and emerging technologies in the ICT industry, skill and competency gaps among ICT graduates from HEIs continue to increase exponentially. This dilemma is made worse by the existing misalignment between ICT skillsets offered within graduate and undergraduate programmes, and those the industry expects. To avert this trajectory, industry-aligned ICT re-tooling and re-skilling short courses were identified to suitably fill this gap better because of their shorter review period. To this effect, an industry-aligned ICT short course development framework and implementation tool for HEIs has been developed. This framework and tool will allow for agility in the development and review of ICT short course curriculum to reflect the demands of the marketplace (industry). This study was therefore conducted to determine the constituent elements or processes of an industry-aligned ICT short course development framework (ADDIER Model) and implementation tool (ADDIER tool). Further, to increase stakeholder involvement, teamwork, and collaboration in all ADDIER processes, an information system (IS) has been designed to digitalize and automate these processes within the ADDIER tool. The study being descriptive and explorative, a qualitative research design was preferred comprising of interviews, survey, observation, and desk reviews as data collection methods. Selective sampling was used to qualify research respondents from among stakeholders. The collected data was analysed using data analysis software: Atlas ti,

google forms, and MS Excel. Lucid Charts online application was used to draw UML diagrams for the IS designs. Focused group discussions were used to validate the usability of the developed ADDIER framework, implementation tool and IS designs. The researcher recommends more study to be done using quantitative approaches to validate implicit causal assertions, revise this model for application under institutionalised programmes, and development of the designed system into a prototype for further testing and eventual adoption.

Key Words: Evaluation, Framework, implementation, HEIs tools, Uganda

Introduction

The Skills Framework for the Information Age (SFIA) is a two-dimensional framework consisting of professional skills on one axis and seven levels of responsibility (Follow, Assist, Apply, Enable, Ensure / Advise, Initiate / Influence, Set Strategy / Inspire / Mobilise) on the other. It describes required professional skills at various levels of competence and generic levels of responsibility. The use of SFIA model to assess the skills within an organization or MDAs helps to provide answers to questions such as: ‘what skills do we have which seeks to determine the current skill profile against the desired standards?’ ‘In other words, ‘what skills do we need?’

This offers a way of recognizing and planning to develop a professional career path to the desired goal, SFIA6 (2015). To identify skill competency gaps (professional skills, knowledge, and behaviors required at each level of responsibility), first establish capability baseline within industry or organizations (MDAs) and then determine the desired end for each role to identify competency skill gaps. This model also helps recruiting agencies and HR departments to shift from over-reliance on certificates and qualifications that often only confirm a theoretical understanding of concepts, towards specifying competencies based on having the right skills, knowledge, behaviors, and experience at appropriate levels of responsibility.

The existing programme curriculum development guidelines offered by NCHE completely disregard this important process of identifying competency skills gaps and specifying how the proposed curriculum content will address those gaps as stated in their rationale, learning objectives, and outcomes.

Success areas where SFIA models have been used

“The framework has been used extensively within the Australasian and British private and public sectors to manage organizational ICT skill profiles and job design, define job families and position descriptions, structure staffing, promotion, and remuneration decisions. ICT professionals are encouraged to use SFIA to manage their career progression and professional development. SFIA further serves as the basis of national professional certification schemes in many European countries and Canada”, Kinsky B.R. et al. (2016). SFIA provides a standard benchmark to ensure regional and international recognition of a country’s short course programmes. For instance, the Australian Computer Society (ACS) recommends the use of SFIA to define career roles in curriculum design and management”, ACS (2012, 2016b). SFIA has also been related to institutional quality management processes, which is a key requirement by regulatory and accreditation bodies, Oliver (2013).

Further, Asgarkhani et al. (2016) used the SFIA framework to come up with a model in figure 1 below. This model will be integrated with other ADDIE course development frameworks to develop an industry-aligned ICT short course development framework and Implementation tool for HEIs.

Figure 1: Model for mapping programmes/courses to SFIA (Source: Asgarkhani et al. 2016)

One of the main drawbacks to SFIA model is its inability to stand alone during course curriculum development and management cycle. This weakness of the model has been addressed by leveraging strengths of the revised bloom's taxonomy (RBT) educational framework at the implementation stage. Further, a conceptual scheme or curriculum development below addresses other ADDIE stages.

Methods

Study Design and Settings

Both quantitative and qualitative research approach was preferred to enable the researcher to investigate the involvement of ICT stakeholders in HEI's short courses curriculum planning, design, development, and implementation. ICT stakeholder's experiences were captured in their natural setting to produce a narrative account to help describe, understand, and interpret the meanings of their experiences within the relevant context. The population in which the sample was drawn comprises Academia (lecturers and administrators), ICT Industry (private and public), Alumni, Researchers and Innovators, Government Regulatory Agencies, and ICT Professional associations/bodies. Within the academia, respondents were selected from: Instructors, ICT short course developers, and administrators, current finalist students on one selected ICT undergraduate programme, participants currently undertaking an ICT short course. Within the ICT Industry, respondents were sourced from government agencies in the ICT sector, individuals working for corporate companies in the private sector, HEIs Alumni currently employed in the ICT industry. Desk reviews of currently running strategic plans of key MDAs, tracer studies, NDPII and III, and ICT Skills Training Needs Assessment Report concluded in 2021.

Sample Size and Study Variables

Table 1 indicates determination of the sampling size and data collection methods

Data Collection Method	Sample ICT stakeholders
Interviews	Two (2) respondents were ICT Instructors and short course developers.
	Two (2) respondents were ICT Instructors from the ICT industry.
	Three (3) respondents were administrators or technicians on ICT short course programmes.
	Five (5) respondents were ICT experts (heads of units) in the ICT industry (public and private sector).
	Two (2) respondents were HEI's alumni and employees in the ICT Industry.
	Four (2) respondents from researchers or incubators in ICT field
Survey	Twenty (23) respondents were selected from HEI's finalist students in ICT disciplines, Alumni, Researchers, Academia, and Industry (used online questionnaire).
	Eight (8) respondents selected from thirty (30) HEI's finalist students in ICT disciplines (used hard copy questionnaire).
	Twelve (12) respondents selected from nineteen (19) ICT short course participants.
Desk review	<p>Apart from referenced documents in the literature review, other specific documents reviewed included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two ICT programmes from two institutions contrast the extent to which the latest technologies and skillsets have been captured. • NCHE, NITA-U strategic plans to determine plans by the two regulatory agencies to address the identified gap. • UICT strategic plan as a capacity-building agency under MoICT and UCC. • NCHE tracer study 2019 and Makerere University tracer study 2015 • ICT Skills Training Needs Assessment (STNA, 2021) report to capture a wider context of ICT skill needs nationally.
Observation	To observe curriculum development, implementation, and review processes (for institutionalized and non-institutionalized programmes) are happening in real-time at a selected HEI.

Source: Primary data, 2021

Data Analysis

Both qualitative and quantitative data was composed and planned. The data collected through interviews, desk review and observation method was scrutinized using content analysis manually. Data analysis entailed the processes of inspection, cleansing, transforming, and modeling data, to discover useful information, making conclusions, and providing answers to the posed research questions. Once data from interview guides, survey questionnaires, documents, and observations were collected, it was coded using Atlas ti computer application software corresponding to each research question. The codes were grouped under unique categories or themes.

Results

Table 2: Contrasting ICT skill areas in two ICT programmes at HEI with industry needs

Skills Expected by the Industry	Skill areas covered in an ICT programme in HE institution - X	Skill areas covered in an ICT programme in HE institution - Y
As Listed By STNA Report 2021		
Online collaboration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Basic Computer Skills / Digital literacy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Cloud services	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Graphics and content authoring	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Internet and email	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Basic computer maintenance and trouble shooting	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Virtual Collaboration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Cyber Security	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Enterprise Systems	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Integrated Financial Management System (IFMS)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Social Media	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Data management(Oracle, MySQL, SQL Server.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
E-government	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Strategic IT management	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Mobile and Web technologies	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
System Administration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Software development	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
IT Support	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Computer systems design and analysis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Digital forensics	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Internet of Things	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
International Computer Driving License (ICDL)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Microsoft Certified Solutions Associate (MCSA)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Microsoft Certified Solutions Developer (MCSD)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Microsoft Certified Systems Engineer (MCSE)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Certified Information Systems Auditor (CISA)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Information Technology Infrastructure Library (ITIL)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Certified in Governance of Enterprise IT (CGEIT)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Project Management Professional (PMP)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
PRojects IN Controlled Environments (PRINCE2)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other Skill areas listed by research respondents		
Artificial Intelligence	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Infrastructure Management	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Website Design and development	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Information Security	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Marketing & Communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Networking Administrations and hardware maintenance	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Core infrastructure skills and emerging technologies	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Multimedia	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Critical thinking, Problem solving skills and innovation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Automation/Machine Learning	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Entrepreneurship	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Object oriented Programming languages (Java, C++, Python)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Ecommerce/ Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Mobile Computing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Overall Industry-alignment Score	14/48 (29%)	16/48 (33%)

Source: Primary data, 2021

Results indicate that the ICT programmes run by HE Institutions X and Y are 29% and 33% industry-aligned respectively. This confirms the researcher's argument of the misalignment of ICT skillsets received from graduates of HEIs and those expected by the industry. The developed framework will be able to address this misalignment through stakeholder involvement at all stages of the curriculum development cycle as well as reduce the review period through automation of key processes. Further, retooling and reskilling short courses will be developed using a developed Industry aligned ICT short courses curriculum development framework and implementation tool.

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Source: Primary data, 2021

ICT Short Course Development, Implementation & Review Framework for HEIs (ADDIER Framework)

Components and processes of the ADDIER framework and implementation tool

The Planned curriculum

This stage consists of four elements within a dynamic relationship to each other: The educational philosophy describes which learning theories underpin the choices in teaching and learning strategies to help participants reach the learning outcomes. The learning outcomes are determined by consulting stakeholders who determine the industry relevancy (position) of the skills to be included in the short course curriculum.

Educational Philosophy (or educational purpose and Instruction philosophy)

Informs curriculum decisions by reflecting on the vision, mission, and mandate of the Institution. It also describes which learning theories underpin the choices in teaching and learning strategies. It is important to explain why you will do some things and leave others. Start by answering the 'why questions' before the what, where, how, and when questions. Your institutional motivation informed by your vision, mission and mandate will inform the curriculum choices you make.

Industry Positioning

In a nutshell, what is your value proposition? What unique product or service are you bringing onto the market? Who is your target customer? Who are your competitors in that market segment? Have you done your SWOT and PESTEL analysis? This will inform the scope of your operations and identify the gap in the industry that the course will fill. The output of this process will feed into the development of course learning outcomes.

Learning outcomes

After the educational philosophy has been established and industry positioning determined, it is time to develop learning outcomes. What do you want to see (skills, knowledge, behaviors) happening to your target customers one or two years after consuming your product or service? At this stage, your team should have M&E personnel to help you draft desired impacts and craft measurable performance indicators for specific milestones. It is important to involve key stakeholders with that specific expertise or influence (hopefully you have done your stakeholder analysis at this point). Since learning objectives and activities will to a degree target achieving desired learning outcomes, this stage of the process will determine whether the curriculum will be aligned to the industry needs or not. This stage will also determine eventual professional competencies (in terms of knowledge, skills, and attitudes/behaviors) acquired at various levels of the participant's responsibility. SFIA framework will be very helpful in mapping required professional competencies to learning outcomes and assessments.

Skill Gaps Assessment

Note that having learning outcomes is not very specific. At this stage, we need to determine SMART objectives (three to five) for each learning outcome identified above.

To do this, schedule field visits to that organisation or MDA or representative sample for the industry and conduct a baseline survey against the desired outcome to determine the skills gap. With this visit, you will have answers to questions relative to participants' levels of responsibility such as: what competencies (skills, knowledge, and behaviours) do participants have now? Where do they need to be by the end of a given period? What competency gaps exist?

Short Course Outline (modular format)

This stage determines the content constructed to address the identified gaps and achieve desired competencies. To do so, course and module objectives must be set first, the learning activities to achieve the objectives. It is important to benchmark existing international certifications (in that skill area) for students' motivation to advance and acquire related industry certifications. This will prevent the short course content from falling too short of national and international expectations for accreditation. The subject matter content will be categorized into modules to allow

for relevant resource mobilization for each module. The different module content will then constitute an ICT short course outline. Modules consist of logically structured and sequenced skillsets addressing identified competency gaps to achieve given SMART objectives. At this stage, input from the M&E unit is critical to factor in measurable outputs for evaluating and appraising performance.

The implemented curriculum

This is the stage where final delivery of services to the target participants (consumers) happens. How the elements of this stage are handled will determine the success or failure of the developed curriculum.

Structure and Sequence

The short course modules are then structured or sequenced to suit participant's characteristics and context. It must be logically structured with increasing complexity to match identified professional competencies (knowledge, skills, and behaviors) at the respective levels of responsibility.

Sequencing course modules allow pre-requisite modules to be done before others to provide foundational knowledge that will be assumed in the next module.

Teaching, learning and assessment

Align session objectives and activities using revised Bloom's taxonomy to address increasing levels of complexity for concepts and skills being taught, while remaining aligned to predefined module objectives and outcomes. Assessment should be continuous and scheduled around completed module objective(s) to ensure mastery of concepts and skills in that area, (Litzinger et al. 2011). A blend of online and offline teaching and learning strategies may be adapted to achieve specific course objectives.

Participants' characteristics and resources

The participant's responsibilities should be articulated in the course manual (given to all participants at the beginning of each course) to ensure the smooth running of the short course. These expectations may include minimum attendance, payment plan, adherence to a mode of instruction and assessments, software, and hardware requirements, etc. Given the time constraints associated with short courses and diversity in participants' backgrounds (knowledge, skills, and experience), their needs are defined to assure value-for-money and optimum resource utilization.

Institutional resources

This includes both soft and hard infrastructure. Under soft infrastructure, resources like instructors with the right competencies (knowledge and qualifications, skills and professional experience, behavior), conducive teaching and learning environment, etc. Hard infrastructure may include resources like buildings and equipped computer labs, etc. NCHE programme curriculum development guidelines are useful to benchmark regarding this area.

Course Modules

Modules are a packaging of content addressing identified skill gaps at a given level of responsibility. Modules comprising a short course should be well structured and sequenced to provide logical continuity to the overall short course. Course assessment and evaluation should be done at the end of each module to allow for earlier feedback from participants and module review.

Stakeholder involvement

This process of the curriculum development framework is one of the main pillars that engages at all stages of planning, design, development, and implementation. At the planning stage, stakeholder consultation must be mandatory and dynamic to develop learning outcomes for an ICT short course curriculum that are industry-aligned.

ICT Short Course Development, Implementation & Review Tool for HEIs (ADDIER Tool)

Discussion

Reviewed literature and responses from research respondents revealed that existing curriculum models, frameworks, and schemes do not explicitly address the need for developing and implementing industry-aligned ICT short courses in HEIs. When respondents (who were sampled from stakeholder categories) were asked about any possible existence of frameworks to guide the analysis, design, development, implementation, evaluation, and review and review processes to develop industry-aligned ICT short courses, their responses unanimously indicated the need to develop such a one. A few of the respondent's comments are highlighted below:

"I have not seen any framework that gives clear guidance to all staff who would like to develop ICT short courses", PA13 reiterated.

"There are no approvals by government departments needed for short courses because in most cases, there are no course admissions requirements", PA8 commented.

"What I observed is that most short course outlines are derived from a degree or diploma programmes", PA1 affirmed.

The researchers, therefore, concluded that the need to develop an industry-aligned ICT short courses training framework for HEIs framework and tool is justifiable to provide ICT graduates and Industry experts with opportunities to develop their professional career paths in ICT.

Almost all existing curriculum development models agree on using the ADDIE model that emphasizes Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation processes as cyclic.

Other models have edited the ADDIE model by arguing that the evaluation process should be at the center, and contributing to every other process. However, the existing models do not overtly express the need for conducting impact assessment at the review stage which determines the relevancy of competencies received by participants in the industry.

The modified model should therefore be ADDIER and not ADDIE. Employers and employees need to assess the impact of acquired skillsets as a result of received training on their business goals. Their well-critiqued feedback becomes very crucial in the review of the next ICT short curriculum for better industry alignment. In addition, the revised and proposed framework and tool considers marketing, monitoring, and evaluation to be critical processes that must be integrated within each of ICT short curriculum development and review cycle stages and/or processes for better industry alignment.

One of the critical findings by the researchers was the need to address ICT competency gaps in real-time that were created by the fast-evolving and emerging technologies in the industry. It is important to accurately determine the existing ICT competency gaps in the industry at their respective level of current and desired competencies to design a curriculum that appropriately addresses the identified needs as they evolve.

Most Institutions in reviewed literature argued that focusing on principles of the subject matter instead of technology changes in the industry was the target of their curriculum design, development, and implementation hence allowing their graduates the flexibility to adapt to changing environments.

This approach however ignores the concerns of key industry stakeholders in the curriculum development ecosystem. The revised components of the industry-aligned ICT short course development framework and tool address these concerns by proposing an information system design to actively involve key stakeholders at all processes short course curriculum planning, design, development, implementation, evaluation, and impact assessment.

The designed information system would further reduce the overall short course development and review cycle time, hence responding to the fast-evolving and emerging technologies in the industry in real-time.

Conclusion

This research aimed to develop an industry-aligned ICT short course development framework, implementation tool, and design an Information System to automate stakeholder involvement in the ADDIER processes of the implementation tool.

Further, the study provides a solution to the misalignment between ICT skillsets offered by HEIs and those expected by the industry as a result of fast-evolving and emerging technologies in the industry.

This was achieved by reducing the duration taken to develop and review ICT short courses through digitalization and automation of the ADDIER (analysis, design, development, implementation, evaluation, and review) processes of the modified course development framework and implementation tool.

A qualitative approach (with triangulated data collection methods) research design was employed since the study was descriptive and explorative. This intervention will provide a requisite supply of ICT graduates with the right competencies (skills, knowledge, and behaviors) to fill ICT skill gaps in the industry.

The developed ICT short course development framework, implementation tool, and information system design will also benefit all stakeholders like the academia, participants, instructors, curriculum developers, researchers, innovators, regulators, ICT professional associations, institution management in many unique ways.

Recommendation

- Studying the modified industry-aligned ICT short course development framework, and implementation tool and adapt it to institutionalized long course curriculum development at HEIs.
- Due to the study scope, there is a need to develop the proposed information systems design to be tested and implemented as a web resource accessible by all HEIs in Uganda that offer ICT short courses. This will significantly reduce the duration to develop or review an ICT short course that is industry-aligned.
- Researchers are invited to research information systems for engaging stakeholders during ICT curriculum development and review processes since existing research appears scanty.
- Since the research design was mainly quantitative, there is a need to pursue causative aspects to this study and determine the degree of causation of the implicitly stated hypotheses.
- Researchers are also invited to do a study on what it takes to have a national ICT short course regulatory agency that accredits, provides strategic and operational standards to all HEIs developing and implementing ICT short courses.
- Lastly, HEIs are invited to adopt and adapt this developed ICT short course curriculum development framework and implementation tool in their planning, designing, developing, implementing, evaluating, and reviewing of ICT short courses. This framework and tool's processes have the potential to cut across all disciplines that aim at transitioning their students from graduates to industry career professionals in their respective disciplines.

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